

Narration of Development of Ecotourism in Instagram for City Branding: Study in Pinrang Regency

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ABSTRACT: *City branding is the identity of the city that contains the pride of the population against the city. This pride, for example, can be found in uploads in social media, especially on Instagram. Therefore, a search of these accounts to determine its potential in forming city branding. Qualitative content analysis is performed to identify the strategy of these accounts: insta-Pinrang, pinrangkeren and pinrangupdate to popularize the tourist spots in Pinrang. Furthermore, recognized the potential of these accounts in ecotourism development objectives and the establishment of city branding Pinrang. The results of this study can be a reference for development planners on strategies used in social media to popularize the natural attractions and their potential in the formation of city branding*

KEYWORDS: *narrative analysis, city branding, ecotourism*

I. INTRODUCTION

City branding is the identity of the city that contains the pride of the population against the city. This study intends to (1) Identify Accounts and Determine their potential in forming city branding, and (2) Recognized the potential of these goals in ecotourism development objectives and the establishment of city branding in Pinrang.

Branding is a concept that is one of the important points in marketing a product. Efforts to give brands or branding can be done both for tangible components such as names, logos and packaging as well as those that are intangible, such as atmosphere and image. Furthermore, the brand concept can not only be implemented in a product or service, but can also be implemented for an area. The scope of the area can be within the borders of the country, islands, provinces and cities. The result of research conducted by researchers at TPP show that if a country or city has a superior brand that is different, authentic and has good quality it can improve the image and competitiveness of the country or city

Branding a city is necessary to provide an identity for the city. With the existence of identity, the city will have its own characteristics that ideally are not owned by other cities. A city that does not have uniqueness will not be remembered, has no differentiation and will not be able to compete with other cities. With a strong brand a city can "sell itself" and open up a wider employment field, either through the benefits of tourism (culinary, tourism, crafts, art and culture), as an educational center, as well as an industry advantage that has the potential to attract domestic and foreign investors country.

The impact will have an effect on the increase of Original Regional Income (PAD) and the welfare of the people. Consumer behavior and ethnographic studies expert Amalia Maulana states that strong brands have three important components that are relevant, where brands must fit the needs and wants of consumers or stakeholders. The brand must also be distinctive, which is able to highlight its uniqueness different from its competitors. Third, the brand must be consistent, the brand must be able to optimize and manage the uniqueness

that "sold" so that will always terpatri in the minds of consumers (Maulana.2012: 64). The central government in recent years has intensively encouraged local governments to take more serious branding in various cities in Indonesia

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Building a brand in an area is the same as an effort to create a particular image that is unique to the region in question and at the same time an attempt to distinguish the region from other regions. Brands such as proposed by Louro and Cunha (2001) is a multi-dimensional set of attributes that consists of functional elements, emotional, relational and strategic, where the collectivity of all of these elements form a unique association in the public's mind. (Aaker, 1996: 68). The association will in turn create a brand image or a set of feelings and attitudes that the community has about a brand (Aaker, 1996: 70). In the context of the region, local uniqueness will be the core benefit, characteristics and culture that attract potential stakeholders, such as investors, residents and tourists. Thus the brand of a region may be the region's competitive advantage.

The creation and management of city brands requires integrated efforts. Regarding this matter Kavaratzis (2004) stated the need to adopt the concept of corporate branding to manage the brand of a city through an integrated approach of eight elements of the city:

1. Vision and Strategy: Clarity about the development and future of the city.
2. Internal Culture: All efforts must be oriented to the management and development of city brands and these activities must be internally entrenched.
3. Local Communities: Prioritize and involve local residents, entrepreneurs and business people in developing city brands.
4. Synergy: Seeks agreement and support from all related stakeholders in order to develop the city brand.
5. Infrastructure: Prepare adequate standard infrastructure in accordance with the city brand that has been declared.
6. City landscape: Setting up the city landscape according to the established city brand.
7. Opportunities: Good urban infrastructure and landscape can be a stimulus and an attraction for stakeholders (migrants, tourists, business people, local residents).
8. Communication: City brands are communicated strategically and continuously so that they are embedded in the minds of stakeholders and become a strong identity of a city.

Disseminating city brands that have been declared through strategic marketing communication activities and sustainable and involving all relevant stakeholders. Conventional marketing communications activities (advertisements in local, regional and national print, local and national print, television and radio) and digital marketing communications (Instagram, blog, Facebook, website, line) are optimized In relation to the empowerment of local communities and branding communications, there is an opportunity to establish city branding through posting Instagram accounts.

The potential of ecotourism is chosen as an alternative branding strategy because ecotourism has the opportunity to support sustainable development. Wood (2002: p. 9) mentioned that ecotourism is "Ecotourism is responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and sustain the wellbeing of local people." (The Ecotourism Society, 1991). In addition, IUCN (now called the World Conservation Union) states in 1996 that ecotourism is " environmentally travel and visitation to relatively undisturbed natural areas, in order to enjoy and appreciate nature (and any accompanying cultural features - both past and present) that promotes conservation, socio-economic involvement of local populations."

This study uses qualitative content analysis methods. In many literatures, this method is generally used in nursing studies. For example, on the analytic procedures specific to each approach and techniques for addressing

trustworthiness with hypothetical examples drawn from the area of end-of-life care (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005). According to them, content analysis is a widely used qualitative research technique. The current content analysis application shows three different approaches: conventional, directed, or summative. Summative content analysis involves counting and comparisons, usually keywords or content, followed by interpretations of the underlying context (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005).

Analysis of documents can also be a form of fieldwork. For example, the analysis of ethnographic content is briefly contrasted with conventional modes of analysis of quantitative content to illustrate the usefulness of constant comparisons to find patterns, emphasis, and themes that appear in the analysis of TV news coverage of Iran's hostage situation. The ethnographic perspective may help illustrate the pattern of human action when document analysis is conceptualized as fieldwork (Altheide, 1987). Referring to this study, postings in Instagram accounts are treated as document analyzes to understand the account owner's strategy in popularizing Pinrang, in particular places where ecotourism is potential

In various forms of qualitative content analysis, the theme search is the main one. This study aims to identify the instagram account strategy in popularizing the destination.

As a sample, 3 Instagram accounts were chosen bearing the name Pinrang, namely @pinrangupdate, @insta_pinrang, and @pinrangkeren. These three account posts are sampled. E-observation is done to find out the trends of certain themes that emerge from these posts

Furthermore, the results of content analysis in cross check with indepth interview results and document data from the Department of Tourism, Youth and Sports Pinrang District (dari Dinas Pariwisata, Pemuda dan Olahraga Kabupaten Pinrang) . Field research was conducted in March and July 2018.

III. RESULTS

Digital storytelling in this study refers to the way of the owners of Instagram accounts who popularized beautiful places in Pinrang telling their story about Pinrang. In communication studies, it was noted that generally the digital story focuses on a particular topic. From certain standpoint, therefore, these might be a certain strategy.

@pinrangupdate

This account reposts more varied content. In addition to images of the Ammani Beach scene, for example, @pinrangupdate also reposted places like PuncakKARomba, PLTA Bakar, dan Soroja House. This may be related to the tagline as an account that presents "Tourism, customs, history and news"

Puncak Karomba is a spot in Pinrang that is famous as "Land in the Cloud" like the same place in Tana Toraja. However, based on document search, Puncak Karomba does not include superior destinations of Pinrang Regency. Subsequent searches through interviews with officials in the relevant offices mentioned that Puncak Karomba can not be developed by the government because it is owned by the private sector and in a dispute condition.

Bakar Water Power Plant is a dam and irrigation source that irrigates Pinrang and surrounding districts. This place does not have special access as a tourist spot, but the post-images create curiosity and awe. Bakar hydropower is not included as a tourist destination based on the Tourism Office document. Soroja's house is a kind of old royal house in Pinrang. This spot is generally unknown. This spot is also not included in the flagship destination. Field observations show old houses that are not groomed and look mediocre. The last three places mentioned are famous in social media but are not commonly visited by local tourists. There is no adequate

access, bad infrastructure and no management. The post theme @pinrangupdate during January - June 2018 is a place, activity and cultural heritage. This can be a potential to further enrich the insight about Pinrang.

@instapinrang

This account uses the tagline "Let's remember Pinrang Through photos". Using the 'photo of the day' strategy that is reposted from other people's posts. During January to June 2018, @instapinrang me-repost 34 places that have beautiful scenery in Pinrang. From all posts, most posted are Kalijodoh Waterfall, IttoSarassa, and LattaPituWaterfall. AirTerjunLattaPitu

In some posts, there are captions included

1. The hills of Lembang area of Bungi village

"Buttunabuttu. Kampong na kampong salulattungtasi 'Ada 'sola Budaya. Sipulungmanangmancaji mesa wilaya, sanganna PENRANG / KAB.PINRANGDanKEC.LEMBANG" Daerah yang bisaAndamasukisebagaitempattujuanwisataKab.Pinrang, banyaksurgatersembunyiygada di LEMBANG, cumanbeberapaygbisasyaratnya.Hanyapemerintah yang tidakbiasadenganitu. (The area that you can enter as a tourist destination of Pinrang Regency, many hidden paradise in here, but only a few can be the conditions. Only the government whose unusual with that.)

2. Wakka Beach

Jikakauadalahmentarimaka bias senja yang tersisaadalahkenangantentangmu. Indah meskikausudahtidakada - FiersaBesari If you are a sun then the remaining twilight bias is a memory of you. Beautiful even though you are gone - Fiersa Besari)

3. Waterfall KalijodohPinrang

Alamsemestainimemilikibatas, tapihikmah yang bisadiperikpadanyatakerbatas. This universe has limits, but the wisdom that can be plagued to it is infinite.

4. Pantai Harapan (Ammani)

Menara tempattmemantau 'mantan The tower where you can monitor your ex

According to respondents interviewed, this increases the attractiveness of the post. However, the existence of the caption may be due to re-post from the post following caption. Caption also contains criticism to the government as seen in the post about the hills of Lembang area of Bungi village

The post theme @instapinrang is more of a view. Postings are also diverse, including beaches, waterfalls, parks and artificial attractions such as floating houses. The number of posts and the frequency of posting more allows the variation.

@pinrangkeren

Similar to @instapinrang, @pinrangkeren also includes LattaPituWaterfall ;; Kali Jodoh Waterfall, KarawaWaterfallLosita Beach, and Ammani Beach. However, that is not found in @instapinrang, @pinrangkeren contains posts about Peak Karomba, district. Lembang.Scene @pinrangkeren posts are all postings containing photographs of people pose; not merely the associated natural scenery.

This accommodates the need for people to use social media to 'show themselves' and are often known as narcissism. This can be a strategy for @pinrangkeren to get more viewers and followers; or also add human elements with the impression of human activity in the intended place.

However, to this day, this assumption cannot be checked to the manufacturer of the message because it has not received an answer.

For tourism marketing, sources from government experts suggest maximizing the role of young social media users.

"Harusnyapemerintahbisamengidentifikasi keinginan anak-anak mudakemudianketikamerekasudahbisabersuaratentangapa yang diainginkan, padadasarnyasecaraemosionalsudahmembangkitkanpartisipasinya.Padasaat yang bersamaan, pemerintahisebenarnyabisamenyisipkanapapesan yang diinginkanolehpemerintah, misalnyapemerintahmenginginkan, apa..anakmudainiturutmempromosikanmelalui media sosialjadisecaralangsungmaupuntidaklangsunganakmudainilah yang mengangkat branding kota, sayapikir di Makassar juga sepertiitu."

"The government should be able to identify the wishes of young people then when they can speak out about what they want, basically emotionally they have raised their participation. At the same time, the government can actually insert what the government wants, for example, the government wants, what ... these young people also promote through social media so it is directly and indirectly this young person who raises city branding, I think in Makassar is like that too. "

The use of social media in Pinrang tourism marketing was also suggested by the speakers at the FGD.

"Ah..sayalebih.. mungkinkalosayalebihberpikirebegini.. bagaimanakitamemanfaatkanapa yang kitamiliki, apa yang kitapunya gitu. Nah, terkaitpenyebaraninformasi ini, tadipagisudahsempatsayasebutkan, adapotensi yang sangatbesar yang dimilikiolehpemerintahdaerah, ah..adatiga. Yang pertama ah..jumlahkaryawan.. jumlah ASN, di KabupatenPinrang, initalipagisayadapat info kuranglebih 6 ribu.. hampir 7 ribu ASN. Yang keduaadalahmasyarakatumum yang aktifmenggunakan media sosial.Jadi, fokusnyainike media sosialkarenamenurut ah..menurutpandangan kami, media sosialiniadalahsalahsatusaranapenyebaraninformasi yang sangatmurahketimbangmungkinBapakdariKominfobisamereviewbelanjamedianyapemerintahdaerah, selamainibagaimana. Nah, memanfaatkan media sosialinibisasangatmurah, sepertiitu.Kemudian yang ketigaadalah para pengusaha-pengusaha lokal yang juga memafaatkan media sosialsebagai ah..saranapromosiusahamereka. Ah..initiga.. tiga.. ah.. tigaasetini, kalobolehsayakatakan, tigaasetinimerupakan ah.. alat yang sangat ah.. istilahnya.. bisaefektifdanmurahuntukpenyebaraninformasi. Sebagaicontoh, aplikasi.."

Ah ... I'm more ... maybe if I think more like this ... how we use what we have, what we have that way. Now, related to the dissemination of this information, I mentioned earlier this morning, there is a huge potential that the local government has, ah ... there are three. The first one ... the number of employees ... the number of ASNs, in Pinrang Regency, this morning I got info about 6 thousand ... almost 7 thousand ASN. The second is the general public who actively use social media. So, the focus is on social media because according to ah .. in our view, this social media is one of the means of disseminating information that is very cheap rather than maybe the Father of Communication and Information can review the media expenditure of the local government, what have we done. Well, using social media can be very cheap, like that. Then the third is local entrepreneurs who also use social media as a means of promoting their business. Ah ... here are three ... three ... ah ... these three assets, if I may say, these three assets are ah ... very good tools ... the term ... can be effective and inexpensive for information dissemination. For example, application...

IV. CONCLUSION

Those three accounts that become the sample is very potential as a forum for dissemination of citybranding and popularizing ecotourism in Pinrang Regency. The government and stakeholders can cooperate with these account owners as influencers on social media.

Storytelling strategy is carried out by repost and involves the participation of the accounts of others who had traveled in Pinrang experience or pay attention to Pinrang. This participation is a great social capital to develop the potential of ecotourism and further forming Pinrang citybranding which is more integrative with all internal or external parties of Pinrang.

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